

EVALUATION OF COMPUTABILITY CRITERIONS FOR RUNTIME WEB SERVICE INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT

Today's competitive environment drives the enterprises to extend their focus and collaborate with their business partners to carry out the necessities. Tight coordination among business partners assists to share and integrate the service logic globally. But integrating service logics across diverse enterprises leads to exponential problem which stipulates developers to comprehend the whole service and must resolve suitable method to integrate the services. It is complex and time-consuming task. So the present focus is to have a mechanized system to analyze the Business logics and convey the proper mode to integrate them. There is no standard model to undertake these issues and one such a framework proposed in this paper examines the Business logics individually and suggests proper structure to integrate them. One of the innovative concepts of proposed model is Property Evaluation System which scrutinizes the service logics and generates Business Logic Property Schema (BLPS) for the required services. BLPS holds necessary information to recognize the correct structure for integrating the service logics. At the time of integration, System consumes this BLPS schema and suggests the feasible ways to integrate the service logics. Also if the service logics are attempted to integrate in invalid structure or attempted to violate accessibility levels, system will throw exception with necessary information. This helps developers to ascertain the efficient structure to integrate the services with least effort.

Keywords

Business Logic Model, Service Integration, Business Logic Property Evaluation System, Computability and Traceability Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the trend in economic globalization and enormous development in information technology, the demand for information and logic sharing has become more serious which urges the companies to collaborate closely with their business partners to gain access to needed information and business logic. Over the past decade, the companies have been using various technologies and products in an attempt to support collaboration. These solutions vary from basic point-to-point connection approach such as EDI, expensive ERP systems such as Rossetanet, ebXML, etc. The current technologies semi-automatically integrate the services and it needs manual intervention in number of areas. It requires developers to analyze the service to identify possible way for integration. It is a complex task which needs developers to understand both service and identify better way for integration. Also the present technologies does not consider how to composite of services and how to describe the service contracts. We proposed Business Logic model to face these brutal challenge and complexities.

The proposed model enables the automation of service integration by coordinating sequences of tasks and supports sophisticated exception management. The proposed Business Logic Model uses property evaluator method to evaluate the service to ascertain correct structure for integration. It analyses at which level service fulfills particular property in functionality level and also as per contract, accordingly develops flow diagram as it reflects property evaluation outcome. Then BLP (Business Logic Property) schema is generated from this diagram holding necessary information for integration. While integration, System utilizes this BLP schema to identify proper structure for integration and to spot various actions can be carried out with the service. With this flocked information from BLP schema, it integrates the service automatically. If services are integrated as violating contract or with invalid structure, the system will throw exception with necessary information. End-to-end security is provided by annotating service descriptions with security objectives used to generate convenient Quality of Protection Agreements between partners. Conversely, agreements are processed by a dedicated matching module with respect to security requirements stated by the SLA. In addition to this, we need a mechanism to monitor the resource while sharing to adapt the modifications made by the developers. Source control Management tracks the modification and facilitates impact analysis between the existing and modified services that ensures computability criteria. The source control management system allows us to see the historical background behind the changes made to the business logic of the web services. This helps the developers to see where the changes have been progressively made and include or remove the change as per the need. Thus this would be a powerful and easiest model for developers to integrate the services. Here we demonstrated service integration with BLP schema generation for banking application using Netbeans IDE.

2. RELATED WORKS

In this section, we discuss various research work and different solutions exist in the market for service integration. Zuoren Jiang proposed a model called 'Multi-layer Structure for Dynamic Service Integration (MSFDSI)' in SOA which adds authorized institution and a service integration & analysis adapter to achieve the service authorization, service analysis and dynamic service integration. Service integration & analysis adapter analyses and search the service that can meet the service requestor's requests according to service contracts stated by authorized institution [1]. W.J.Yan proposed B2B integration approach for SME which provides a feasible and cost-effective B2Bi solution for SMEs by leveraging the characteristics of Web Services. It utilizes pull and push mechanisms for effective information exchange and sharing between trading partners. This approach has been incorporated in a B2Bi Gateway which enables SMEs to participate in business-to-business collaboration by making use of Web Services [2]. Liyi Zhang proposed a model called WSMX (Web Service Modeling execution), a software system that enables the creation and execution of Semantic Web Services based on the Web Service Modeling Ontology (WSMO) for enterprise application integration. It improves Service discovery, simplifies change management and supports semi-automatic service composition and enhanced interoperability between services [3]. Thomas Haselwanter presented a model based on the WSMX was build to tackle heterogeneities in RosettaNet messages by using the axiomatised knowledge and rules. It supports communication between partners, data and process mediation using WSMX integration middleware[4]. Jianwei Yin proposed an ESB framework for large scale Service Integration, JTangSynergy adopts several mechanisms for providing effective and efficient dependability. It enables automated recovery from component failures and robust execution of composite services by checking service compatibility [5].

Gulnoza Ziyaeva proposed framework to enable the content-based intelligent routing path construction and message routing in ESB which defines the routing tables and mechanisms of message routings and facilitate the service selection based on message content [6]. Soo Ho Chang proposed a framework for dynamic composition on Enterprise Service Bus which consists of four elements; Invocation Listener, Service Router, Service Discoverer, and Interface Adapter. This

framework enables the runtime discovery and composition of published services without altering the client side applications [7]. Liu Ying presents a unified service composition framework to support business level service composition. An intelligent service composer based on this unified service composition framework is developed to enable business level service composition by business people under the help of some advanced technologies, including intelligent service components searching, automatic service compliance checking, and template-based service adaptation [8]. In addition, Companies use different solutions exist in the market for Business to business application framework, including EDI, RosettaNet, ebXML etc. EDI: A seminal event in B2B evolution was the development of electronic data interchange (EDI), whereby trading partners established standard formats for the exchange of electronic documents to facilitate electronic transactions. Trading partnerships between two firms using EDI are well defined and is used for automated replenishment and efficient supply chains[9]. RosettaNet: The RosettaNet consortium develops XML-based business standards for supply chain management in the information technology and electronic component industries. It defines the business processes and provides the technical specifications for data interchange. RosettaNet standards comprise Dictionary, RNIF (RosettaNet Implementation Framework) and PIP (Partner Interface Process)[10][11]. ebXML: The electronic business XML (ebXML) provides a complete framework for setting up B2B collaborations. It is a set of documents, with several prototype completed, enabling businesses of any size to do business electronically with anyone else. The ebXML specifications cover almost the entire B2B collaboration process: collaboration Protocol Profile (CPP), Collaboration Protocol Agreement (CPA), Business Process Specification Schemas (BPSS), Messaging, Registry/repository and a core Component [12]. Above works paves way to semi-automatically integrate the services across enterprise. But still there is no mechanism to monitor the services while sharing and to routinely guide the developers to integrate according to SLA. Here we demonstrated service integration with BLP schema generation for banking application using Netbeans IDE.

3 BUSINESS LOGIC MODEL

Figure 1 depicts detailed architecture and illustrates how enterprises integrate their services dynamically. Let Enterprise A sends request to share Enterprise B's service, Message broker receives and validates the request, identifies required services from service registry by applying set of rules and delivers the necessary information regarding the identified services to communication handler. Communication handler calls integration bus to deliver the created service proxy to the requestor. Integration bus, a key component of SOA, supports asynchronous messaging, document exchange and above all provides powerful platform for connecting different applications together enabling seamless integration between components. Before delivering the service proxy to the requestor, it assesses the security issue by firing the trigger to the Functional analyzer.

Functionality analyzer analyzes Service Level Agreement (SLA) and policy defined between the two enterprises, identifies the list of constraints for integrating the service. Through this it scrutinizes the security gap between approved security policies and created service proxy and transmits the result to integration bus. Subsequently, integration bus handovers the proxy to the requestor. When requestor attempts to integrate the service, Property evaluation, heart of this model, validates integrating service with various constraints listed out by Functional analyzer to achieve the interoperability goals such as union, substitution, composition, finiteness, enhancement and configuration, etc.... We will see the process of property evaluation detailly in next section. Evaluation metrics holds set of formulas to measure the activities and performance of service integration in order to achieve the interoperability goals efficiently. Business logic and rules are shared in such a way integration policy and interoperability goals are satisfied. Service integration allows sharing the service according to the specified evaluation metrics and integration policy through the created service proxy.

4 Property Evaluation for Service Integration

4.1 Computability

Computability is an essential criterion in web service which determines whether the modified service is computable within a time limit.

Example The requirement is to create a service, e-payment to calculate total price for the list of purchased items and to transact the calculated amount. In the existing shopping application, we have billing service which computes total cost for the purchased items and transaction service in banking application transacts the amount. By integrating these two services, required new service e-payment can be developed. Here integration should be done in such a way that the processing time of the integrated service bounded within a time limit.

logic 1

```
BL1: public string billing(){
BF1: String username=username.get();
String password=password.get();
DRf1: String sql="select * from shopping where username="+username+" and
password="+password;
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery(sql);
CRr1: if(rs.next()){
BFr1: double amount=calculateamount();
String accno=accountno.get();
BFr2 String accno1=123456;
BFf1: String result="Amount to be paid="+amount;
P1: return result;
}}
```

logic 2

```
BL2: public string transact(){
BF21 String accno=accno.get();
String accno1=accno1.get();
String amount=amount.get();
BF22 String transid1=transid.set();
DRf1 Statement st=con.createStatement();
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("select Balance from bank where Accountno='"+accno+"'");
DRr1 double balance=rs.getDouble("Balance");
CRr1 if( (balance-amount)>1000 ){
DRr1 st.executeUpdate("update bank set balance= balance- "+amount+" where
Accountno='"+accno+"'");
DRr2 st.executeUpdate(update bank set balance= balance+" "+amount+" where
Accountno='"+accno1+"'");
BFf1 String transid=" Amount"+amount+"transferred from"+accno+" to "+accno1;
BFr2 String result="Ur transaction id is "+transid1+" Ur transaction completed successfully";
P2 return result;}
```

Solution : Integrated logic

```
BL1 public string ebilling(){
BF11 String username=username.get();
String password=password.get();
DRf11: String sql="select * from shopping where username="+username+" and
password="+password;
```

```

ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery(sql);
CRlfr1 if(rs.next()){
BFlfr1 double amount=calculateamount();
String accno=accountno.get();
String accno1=123456;
BFlfr1 transact(accno,amt,accno1);}
BL2 public String transact(String accno, double amt, String accno1){
BFl1 String transid1=transid.get();
DRlfr1ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("select Balance from bank where Accountno='"+
accno+"'");
DRlfr1 double balance=rs.getDouble("Balance");
CRlfr1 if( (balance-amount)>1000){
DRlfr1String sql="update bank set balance= balance- "+amount+" where
Accountno='"+accno+"'";
st.executeUpdate(sql);
DRlfr1 sql="update bank set balance= balance+"+amount+" where Accountno='"+accno1+"'";
st.executeUpdate(sql);
Plfr1String transid=" Amount"+amount+"transferred from"+accno+" to "+accno1;
Plfr2String result= "Ur transaction id is "+transid1+" Ur transaction completed successfully";}

```

Logic Flow Diagram

$BL_1 \rightarrow \{ BF_1 \}$ $BL_2 \rightarrow \{ [BF_{lfr1}, BF_{11}] \}$ $BL_{T1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{11} \}$
 $BF_1 \rightarrow \{ DR_{f1} \}$ $BF_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{lfr1} \}$ $BF_{11} \rightarrow \{ BF_{lfr1} \}$ $BF_{11} \rightarrow \{ DR_{lfr1} \}$
 $DR_{f1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{r1} \}$ $DR_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{lfr1} \}$ $DR_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{lfr1} \}$
 $CR_{r1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{r1} \}$ $CR_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ [DR_{lfrf1}], [BF_{lfr1}] \}$ $CR_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{lfr1} \}$
 $BF_{r1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{f1} \}$ $DR_{lfrf1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{lfrf1} \}$ $BF_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{lfrf1} \}$
 $BF_{f1} \rightarrow \{ P_1 \}$ $DR_{lfrf1} \rightarrow \{ P_{lfrf1} \}$ $BF_{lfrf1} \rightarrow \{ BL_{T2} \}$
 $BL_{T2} \rightarrow \{ [BF_{lfr1}, BF_{11}], BF_{11} = BF_{lfr1} \}$
 $BF_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{lfr1} \}$ $BF_{11} \rightarrow \{ BF_{lfr1} \}$
 $DR_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{lfr1} \}$
 $CR_{lfr1} \rightarrow \{ [DR_{lfrf1}], [BF_{lfr1}] \}$
 $DR_{lfrf1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{lfrf1} \}$
 $DR_{lfrf1} \rightarrow \{ P_{lfrf1} \}$

billing \rightarrow {get} transaction \rightarrow {get,set} billing \rightarrow {get}
 get \rightarrow {r:select} get \rightarrow {r:select} get \rightarrow {r:select}
 r:select \rightarrow {r:cmp} r:select \rightarrow {r:cmp} r:select \rightarrow {r:cmp}

r:cmp → {compute}	r:cmp → {r:update1,r:update2}	r:cmp → {compute}
compute → {store}	{r:update1, r:update2} → {store}	compute → {store}
store → {return}	store → {return}	store → {transaction}
		transaction → {set,get} get=compute
		get → { r:select}
		r:select → {r:cmp}
		r:cmp → {[r:update1, r:update2]}
		{r:update1, r:update2} → {store}
		store → {return}

BLPS of Logic 1

```

1  <service name="billing">
2  <property>
3    <computability CF="BF1, BF2, BF3, BF4, BF5, DR1, CR1"/>
4  </property>
5  <function name="get" type="input" index="BF1">
6    <param1 name="username" datatype="string" value="null"/>
7    <param2 name="password" datatype="string" value="null"/>
8  </function>
9  <rule index="DR1" name="select" type="data manipulation" dbname="shopping" >
10 <conditions set:status=true>
11 <condition1 Lvar="db.username" expr="&eq" rvar="$username" />
12 <condition2 Lvar="db.password" expr="&eq" rvar="$password" />
13 </conditions>
14 <retrieve param1="accno"/>
15 </rule>
16 <rule index="CR1" name="if" type="conditional" condition:status=true>
17 <function index="DF1" name="compute" action="call" target-function="compute() return-type="double" store-result="amount" />
18 <function index="BFR2" name="set" type="set" >
19 <param name="accno1" value="123456"/>
20 </function>
21 <function index="BFF1" name="assign" type="output" <param name="result" return-type="double" value="amount"/>
22 </rule>
23 </service>

```

BLPS of Logic 2

```

1  <service name="transact" >
2  <property>
3    <computability CF="BF21,DRf1,CRr1,DRrr1, DRrr2"/>
4  </property>
5  <function name="get" type="input" index="BF21">
6    <param1 name="accno" datatype="string" value="null"/>
7    <param2 name="accno1" datatype="string" value="null"/>
8    <param2 name="amount" datatype="double" value="null"/>
9  </function>
10 <rule index="DRf1" name="select" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
11 <condition1 Lvar="db.accountno" expr="&eq" rvar="$accountno" />
12 <retrieve param1="balance"/>
13 <rule index="CRr1" name="if" type="conditional">
14 <condition Lvar="$balance" $amount expr="&gt;" rvar="1000"/>
15 <rule index="DRrr1" name="update" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
16 <condition Lvar="db.accountno" expr="&eq" rvar="$accno" />
17 <assign Lvar="balance" expr="&eq" rvar="($balance $amount) />
18 </rule>
19 <rule index="DRrr2" name="update" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
20 <condition Lvar="db.accountno" expr="&eq" rvar="$accno1" />
21 <assign Lvar="balance" expr="&eq" rvar="($balance+ $amount) />
22 </rule>
23 <function index="BFF1" name="assign" type="output" <param name="transid" return-type="double" value="transstat"/>
24 </rule>
25 </service>

```


4.3 Accessibility

Definition: Accessibility defines the extent to which one service can access the other service's logic.

Example:

The requirement is to create a new service, e-payment to calculate total price for the list of purchased items and to transact the calculated amount. In the existing shopping application, we have billing service which computes total cost for the purchased items and transaction service in banking application transacts the amount. By integrating these two services, required new service e-payment can be developed. Here integration should be done in such a way transaction service could access only the information returned by billing service, it should not view customer's credential information.

logic1:

```
BL1: public string billing(){
BF11: String username=username.get();
      String password=password.get();
DRfl1: String sql="select * from shopping where username="+username+" and
      password="+password;
      ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery(sql);
CRlfr1: if(rs.next()){
BFlfr1: double amount=calculateamount();
      String accno=accountno.get();
      String accno1=123456;
BFlfrf1: String result="Amount to be paid="+amount;
Plfrff1: return result;
      }}

```

logic 2;

```
BL2: public string transact(){
BF11 String accno=accno.get();
      String accno1=accno1.get();
      String amount=amount.get();
      String transid1=transid.create();
DRfl1 Statement st=con.createStatement();
      ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("select Balance from bank where Accountno='"+
      accno+"'");
DRlfr1 double balance=rs.getDouble("Balance");
CRlfr1 if( (balance-amount)>1000 ){
DRlfrf1 st.executeUpdate("update bank set balance= balance- "+amount+" where
Accountno='"+accno+"'");
DRlfrf2 st.executeUpdate(update bank set balance= balance+" "+amount+" where
Accountno='"+accno1+"'");
BFlfr1 String transid=" Amount"+amount+"transferred from"+accno+" to "+accno1;
BFlfrf2 String result= "Ur transaction id is "+transid1+" Ur transaction completed
      successfully";
Plfrf1 return result;
}

```

Integrated logic:

```
BL1 public string ebilling(){
BF11 String username=username.get();
      String password=password.get();

```

```

DRif1: String sql="select * from shopping where username="+username+" and
password="+password;
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery(sql);
CRifr1 if(rs.next()){
BFifr1 double amount=calculateamount();
String accno=accountno.get();
String accno1=123456;
BFifr1 transact(accno,amt,accno1);
}
BL2 public String transact(String accno, double amt, String accno1){
BF11 String transid1=transid.get();
DRif1ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("select Balance from bank where Accountno='"+
accno+"'");
DRifr1 double balance=rs.getDouble("Balance");
CRifr1 if( (balance-amount)>1000 ){
DRifr1String sql="update bank set balance= balance- "+amount+" where
Accountno="+accno+"";
st.executeUpdate(sql);
DRifr1 sql="update bank set balance= balance+"+amount+" where Accountno="+accno1+"";
st.executeUpdate(sql);
Pifr1String transid=" Amount"+amount+"transferred from"+accno+" to "+accno1;
Pifr2String result= "Ur transaction id is "+transid1+" Ur transaction completed successfully";}
    
```


$BL_1 \rightarrow \{ BF_{11} \}$
 $BF_{11} \rightarrow \{ DR_{if1} \}$
 $DR_{if1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{ifr1} \}$
 $CR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{ifr1} \}$
 $BF_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{ifr1} \}$
 $BF_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ P_{ifr1} \}$
 $BL_2 \rightarrow \{ [BF_{if1}, BF_{11}] \}$
 $BF_{if1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{ifr1} \}$
 $DR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{ifr1} \}$
 $CR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ [DR_{ifr1}, [BF_{if1}]] \}$
 $DR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{ifr1} \}$
 $DR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ P_{ifr1} \}$

$BL_1 \rightarrow \{ BF_{11} \}$
 $BF_{11} \rightarrow \{ DR_{if1} \}$
 $DR_{if1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{ifr1} \}$
 $CR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{ifr1} \}$
 $BF_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ BF_{ifr1} \}$
 $BL_2 \rightarrow \{ [BF_{if1}, BF_{11}] \}$
 $BF_{if1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{ifr1} \}$
 $DR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ CR_{ifr1} \}$
 $CR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ [DR_{ifr1}, [BF_{if1}]] \}$
 $DR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ DR_{ifr1} \}$
 $DR_{ifr1} \rightarrow \{ P_{ifr1} \}$

billing→{get}	transaction→{get,set}	billing→{get}
get→{r:select}	get→{r:select}	get→{r:select}
r:select→{r:cmp}	r:select→{r:cmp}	r:select→{r:cmp}
r:cmp→{compute}	r:cmp→{r:update1, r:update2}	r:cmp→{compute}
compute→{store}	{r:update1, r:update2}→{store}	compute→{store}
store→{return}	store→{return}	store→{transaction}
		transaction→{set,get}get=compute
		get→{r:select}
		r:select→{r:cmp}
		r:cmp→{[r:update1, r:update2]}
		{r:update1, r:update2}→{store}
		store→{return}

Logic 1

```

1 <service name="billing">
2   <property>
3     <Accessibility AF="CRr1,BFf1" NAF="BF1,BFf1,BFr2_DR1"/>
4   </property>
5   <function name="get" type="input" index=BF1>
6     <param1 name=username datatype='string' value=null/>
7     <param2 name=password datatype='string' value=null/>
8   </function>
9   <rule index=DR1 name='select' type='data manipulation' dbname="shopping" >
10    <condition1 Lvar= db.uscrname expr= &eq rvar=$username />
11    <condition2 Lvar= db.password expr=&eq rvar=$password />
12    </condition>
13    <retrieve param1=accno/>
14  </rule>
15  <rule index=CR1 name="if" type="conditional" conditionstatus=true>
16    <function index=BF1 name=compute " action='call' target-function=compute() return-type="double" store-result=amount />
17    <function index=BF2 name=sst type=sct >
18      <param name=accno1 value="123456"/>
19    </function>
20    <function index=DF1 name=assign type=output>
21      <param name=result returntype=double value=amount/>
22    </function>
23  </rule>
24 </service>
25

```

Logic 2

```

1 <service name="transact" >
2   <property>
3     <Accessibility AF="BF21" NAF="BF21,DRf1,CRr1,DRrr1, DRrr2"/>
4   </property>
5   <function name="get" type="input" index=BF21>
6     <param1 name=accno datatype='string' value=null/>
7     <param2 name=accno1 datatype='string' value=null/>
8     <param2 name=amount datatype='double' value=null/>
9   </function>
10  <rule index=DRf1 name="select" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
11    <condition1 Lvar= db.accountno expr= &eq rvar=$accountno />
12    <retrieve param1=balance/>
13    <rule index=CRr1 name="if" type="conditional">
14      <condition Lvar=$balance-$amount expr=&gt rvar=1000/>
15      <rule index=DRrr1 name="update" type="data manipulation"
16        dbname="bank" >
17        <condition Lvar= db.accountno expr= &eq rvar=$accno />
18        <assign Lvar=balance expr=&eq rvar=($balance-$amount) />
19      </rule>
20      <rule index=DRrr2 name="update" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
21        <condition Lvar= db.accountno expr= &eq rvar=$accno1 />
22        <assign Lvar=balance expr=&eq rvar=($balance+$amount) />
23      </rule>
24    <function index=BFf1 name=assign type=output>
25      <param name=transid returntype=string value=transstat/>
26    </function>
27  </rule>
28 </service>

```

```

1 <service name="s-billing">
2   <property>
3     <computable CP-CRr1,DFr1,NCF-DFl,DFr1,DFr2,DF21,DR1,DR1,CRr1,DFr1,DFr2/>
4   </property>
5   <service name="billing">
6     <function name="get" type="input" index="BFl">
7       <param1 name="username" datatype="string" value="null"/>
8       <param2 name="password" datatype="string" value="null"/>
9     </function>
10    <rule index="DR1" name="select" type="Data Manipulation" dbname="shopping" >
11      <condition lvar="db.status" expr="true"/>
12      <condition lvar="db.username" expr="eq rvar=$username" />
13      <condition lvar="db.password" expr="eq rvar=$password" />
14    </condition>
15    <retrieve param1=acctno/>
16  </rule>
17  <rule index="CRr1" name="if" type="conditional" condition="STATUS=TRUE">
18    <function index="DFr1" name="compute" action="call" target="function=compute()" return="double" store="result=amount" />
19    <function index="DFr2" name="set" type="set" >
20      <param name="acctno" value="123456"/>
21    </function>
22    <function index="DFr1" name="call" type="invoke" target="service=transact">
23      <arg name="acctno" returnType="string">
24        <arg name="acctno" returnType="string">
25        <arg name="amount" returnType="double">
26      </function>
27    </rule>
28  </service>
29  <service name="transact">
30    <function name="receive" >
31      <arg name="acctno" datatype="string">
32      <arg name="amount" returnType="string">
33      <arg name="amount" datatype="double">
34    </function>
35    <function name="get" type="input" index="BFl">
36      <param1 name="acctno" datatype="string" value="acctno"/>
37      <param2 name="acctno" datatype="string" value="acctno1"/>
38      <param3 name="amount" datatype="double" value="amount"/>
39    </function>
40    <rule index="DR" name="select" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
41      <condition lvar="db.accountno" expr="eq rvar=$acctno1" />
42    <retrieve param1=balance/>
43  </rule>
44  <rule index="DR1" name="if" type="conditional">
45    <condition lvar="db.balance-$amount" expr="gt rvar=1000">
46      <rule index="DR1" name="update" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
47        <condition lvar="db.accountno" expr="eq rvar=$acctno" />
48        <assign lvar="balance" expr="eq rvar-($balance-$amount)" />
49      </rule>
50    </condition>
51  </rule>
52  <rule index="DR1" name="update" type="data manipulation" dbname="bank" >
53    <condition lvar="db.accountno" expr="eq rvar=$acctno1" />
54    <assign lvar="balance" expr="eq rvar-($balance+$amount)" />
55  </rule>
56  <function index="DFr1" name="assign" type="output">
57    <param name="transactid" returnType="double" value="TRANRRAT"/>
58  </function>
59 </service>
60 </service>

```

Here BL₂ can access only the highlighted part of service BL₁.

5. IMPLEMENTATION METHODOLOGY

The web service online payment system is developed by integrating existing billing service and transaction service in banking application as discussed above. Computability and traceability properties are verified as discussed in last section. BPEL diagram of newly developed service is depicted in Fig 2.

Fig 2. Service Integration using BLP schema

6. CONCLUSION

The proposed model provides a powerful platform to share service logic dynamically and securely in such way interoperability between the services is managed. This paper evaluates the services to be integrated with properties such as computability, traceability and accessibility and integrates in efficient way. Also, this model progressively monitors the changes made in the source code and points out whether the changes made affect the computability and traceability criteria's of the web services. Examples given in this paper explains how properties are evaluated for various situations. This would be a standard platform for service providers to share their resources dynamically and securely.

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